

REVIEW ON FACILITATION OF SURPLUS FOOD REDISTRIBUTION USING MOBILE APPLICATIONS

Karnesh S, Pudota Rama Krishna, Jothi Sankar S, Aadil Ahmed Irshath and Anand Prem Rajan*

School of Bio Sciences and Technology,
Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore 632 014, Tamil Nadu, India

***Corresponding Author**

Anand Prem Rajan

Professor

School of Bio Sciences and Technology
VIT, Vellore 632 014

Abstract

Although changes in lifestyle and development in social causes, still hunger remains a great hidden problem in many countries. As a range, it shows almost one-third of the food was wasted, which result in food scarcity, malnutrition, and other several diseases. So many not-for-profit organizations step forward to build a network for rescuing the surplus foods. There are many factors which come to play when rescuing the surplus food. Then these foods need to donate and distribution process changes from place to place and country to country, due to various cultures were followed. In the model world these surplus foods were maintained and distributed through various applications. In that one of the most viable sources was mobile application. This food sharing mobile application shows an interesting high popular now-a-days. These mobile based application moves a step forward and make easier in the food donation and easily connects the non-profit organization and the consumers directly. This paper mainly views on the various not-profit-organization and mobile application data towards the surplus food and the way of working to have a proper food management throughout the society.

Keywords: Surplus, Sustainability, Redistribution, Production, Management, Business, Application.

1. Introduction

Even though the development of civilization and industries, the developed countries too suffer in the food scarcity. In this Australia being one of them and providing a food of 6 million tonnes in which more than 1.9 million feeds were discarded and subjected to landfills. These disposal takes place due to the improper

management of foods, which usually leads to the food scarcity (Nair et al., 2017). These food wastage leads to the greenhouse gas emissions which approximately 70% of global freshwater use. Then it raises the malnutrition to 30-70% globally (Lemaire and Limbourg, 2019). Global food waste is a major obstacle to gradually achieving sustainable development goals like global food security. Global food production uses a lot of resources. It is expected to contribute 19–29% to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Vermeulen et al., 2012). Excessive amounts of food are wasted on a global scale, which can be seen as problematic due to the depletion of resources, the effects of climate change, and the lack of access to food that many face (Messner et al., 2021). UN member states have pledged to reduce the amount of food wasted per person by 50% by 2030 as part of the Sustainable Development Goals (FAO, 2019). This research strand of food waste scholarship, which follows a system thinking approach, concentrates on the main causes of waste creation instead of just the waste material itself. Researchers from the natural science field, using different methods for measuring food waste, have discovered that excessive food production and surplus is a major contributor to food waste on an international level and in financially developed countries (Hall et al., 2009). Consumers and businesses are facing growing public pressure to reduce or eliminate food waste, due to its implications for the environment and economic fairness. The increased social awareness of food waste and its ethical implications have sparked the development of various alternative food provision systems, often referred to as Alternative Food Networks (AFNs). Activities such as farmers' markets, community-supported agriculture, box schemes, solidarity-based purchasing groups, food hubs, urban agriculture, and community gardens are all encompassed by the term Alternative Food Networks. Many efforts are being made to address the issue that a large amount of food is wasted annually while many people still suffer from hunger. These initiatives aim to divert surplus production to consumers or through intermediaries in the supply chain. Sharing and access-based consumption practices are revolutionizing the traditional producer-consumer relationship in the food industry, just like other sectors of the economy (Ertz et al., 2016). Previous research on supply chain management has not considered the link between the use of collaborative technology platforms and the dynamics of buyer-supplier relationships and networks. To conclude, this study has illustrated the structural nature of overproduction beyond the level of individual farmers, suggesting that measures must be taken to address the specific points of lock-in in research, policy, and practice in order to overcome these constraints (Messner et al., 2021).

There are many people, who must suffer from hunger, due to the unavailability of food for them, or the wastage of food by the people, who have it in abundance. Around 9 million people die annually in the whole world, due to hunger. There are various hotels, and restaurants, who daily have excess food, but don't have a platform, where they can donate the excess food, they have. We had taken on the task to prepare an application and a website to act as a point of contact between the donors and the receivers. Our mobile application will function as a social venture that lessens food insecurity, reduces food waste, and promotes social impact. As part of our business strategy, we work with and collaborate with a variety of institutions, such as food donors, non-profits, and governmental bodies, in order to generate money. Also, by highlighting the social effect that our application is having, we want to establish a strong brand identity that connects with our clients and users.

We are hoping to overcome the current food waste due to lack of proper management and redistribution. We plan to work and achieve an ideal goal of 'NO FOOD WASTAGE'. "To a man with an empty stomach, food is God." The first and most important goal of our theme is to act as a link between food donors and the receivers, who suffers from food scarcity due to economic problems. The main goal of our project is to provide a smooth digital platform from where we can get the information about the surplus food. Setting up an app to promote our business and build a positive reputation through marketing and reliable relationships is a priority. We hope to spread awareness among people and create a sustainable society with least food wastage. Technology has the potential to improve food donation procedures in supermarket retail since it speeds up 'donor-recipient' communication, which lowers management responsibility and ensures safe donation.

2. Various Empirical Work on Technology-Assisted Food Sharing

2.1 OLIO

OLIO has resulted in a tremendous reduction in food waste in the UK by reconfiguring traditional supply chain roles of consumers. It is crucial to note that OLIO operates as a pro-social actor on a commercial for-profit footing. Food is commonly shared in the family context (Jaeggi and Gurven, 2013), but kin selection is not obviously at play in the case of OLIO as the vast majority of interactions happen between people that are previously unfamiliar. Tolerated scrounging is the idea that people take food from others without having something to offer in return and that this behaviour is accepted in moderation. Olio was founded by Tessa Cook and Saasha Celestial-One in February 2015(Harvey et al., 2020). it is 'a free app that connects neighbours with each other and with local businesses so surplus food can be shared, not thrown away. This could be food nearing its sell-by date in local stores, spare home-grown vegetables, bread from your baker, or the groceries in your fridge when you go away.'. At the time of writing the application has proved to be extremely successful and is the most popular food sharing mobile application ever created in terms of downloads. Over 13,200 people have volunteered at the time of writing. Volunteers can take on qualitatively different roles in relation to OLIO. Some are encouraged to help advertise and promote the application, whereas others take a 'hands-on' approach and act as intermediaries between businesses and consumers(Mazzucchelli et al., 2021).

Figure 1 - OLIO's Food Savings by Retailer. This statistical bar graph describes about various retailers of OLIO and their contribution in food saving programs. Sainsbury has the highest portion of food saved at about 2 lakhs and Morrison stands second in this list (Harvey et al., 2020).

2.2 Bread and Butter

Bread and Butter Thing is a charity organization based in the United Kingdom that aims to provide food and essential supplies to those in need. The organization was founded in 2013 and has since helped thousands of people struggling with poverty and homelessness. The organization operates through a network of volunteers and donations from the local community. They collect surplus food and other essentials from local businesses and distribute them to those in need. The Bread-and-Butter Thing also provides support services to those who are struggling to make ends meet, including advice on benefits, housing, and employment. The charity has gained significant recognition and support from the local community and businesses. Many companies have partnered with Bread-and-Butter Thing to provide surplus food and other essentials to those in need. The organization also receives significant support from individual donations and volunteers who regularly give their time and resources to help those in need. Bread and Butter Thing has had a significant impact on the lives of many people struggling with poverty and homelessness in the UK. The organization has helped to alleviate food insecurity and provided essential supplies to those in need. It has also provided support services that have helped people to access benefits, housing, and employment. Bread and Butter Thing is an essential charity organization in the UK that is making a significant difference in the lives of those in need. Through the support of the local community, businesses, and volunteers, the organization is helping to address poverty and homelessness in the UK.

2.3 Fareshare

A UK-based company called Fareshare specialises in supplying individuals in need with extra food that manufacturers and merchants no longer need. By developing a more sustainable and equitable food system, their goal is to combat food insecurity and food waste. Fareshare collaborates with several charities, civic associations, and other organisations that fight food insecurity. These collaborations enable them to efficiently deliver meals to a larger audience. The group buys unsold food from wholesalers, merchants, and food producers (Miroso et al., 2016). Following sorting, the food is given to their affiliated groups. All of the food that Fareshare receives and distributes is inspected for safety. They carefully sort and distribute the food with the help of volunteers and qualified employees. Food is redistributed via Fareshare to charities, neighbourhood associations, and other groups that assist the poor. In the UK, food is distributed and stored at a network of depots and hubs. Also, Fareshare generates money to maintain and grow their network. They are financed by contributions from the federal government, businesses, and private citizens (Alexander and Smaje, 2008).

2.4 Neighbourly

Located in the UK, Neighbourly is a social company that aims to cut down on food waste and encourage food redistribution. The activity of the organisation incorporates a number of processes that let companies and non-profits interact and operate efficiently together to redistribute leftover food. Neighbourly also solicits comments from the companies and non-profit organisations engaged in the redistribution of leftover food. This input ensures that the demands of all stakeholders are satisfied and helps to increase the process' efficiency and effectiveness. The redistribution of surplus food by Neighbourly includes a procedure to check the food's quality and safety, connecting surplus food with regional charities, organising food delivery, assessing the impact of the redistribution activity, and obtaining feedback from companies and charities(Reddy, 2001).

Figure 2 - Success Rate of Food Sharing Startups. This bar graph represents the comparative success rate of various food-sharing enterprises and their contribution to food-saving programs. Fareshare has the highest success rate compared to other startups(Reddy, 2001).

Startup	Description	Motive	Partners	Social Impact	Environmental Impact	Future Plan
OLIO	Olío is a digital platform that allows users to share surplus food with others in their local area, reducing food waste and building community connections.	Reduce food waste and build community connections.	Tesco, Sainsbury's, Morrisons, and others.	Helps alleviate food poverty and reduce social isolation.	Reduces greenhouse gas emissions associated with food production and disposal.	Expand the platform and partnerships to further reduce food waste and build community connections.
Bread and Butter	Bread and Butter is a social enterprise that delivers surplus food from local bakeries and cafes to people experiencing food	Reduce food waste and food poverty.	Local bakeries and cafes.	Helps alleviate food poverty and reduce social isolation.	Reduces greenhouse gas emissions associated with food production and disposal.	Expand the delivery service and partner with more local businesses to reach more people in need.
Fareshare	Fareshare is a charity that redistributes surplus food from food businesses to charities and community groups that support people in need.	Reduce food waste and food poverty.	Tesco, Sainsbury's, Asda, and others.	Helps alleviate food poverty and reduce social isolation.	Reduces greenhouse gas emissions associated with food production and disposal.	Increase food redistribution to support more people in need and reduce food waste.
Neighbourly	Neighbourly is a platform that connects businesses with community projects and charities that support social and environmental causes.	Build stronger communities and support social and environmental causes.	Marks & Spencer, Lidl, Aldi, and others.	Helps support social and environmental causes by connecting businesses with community projects and charities.	Reduces environmental impact by promoting sustainability practices.	Continue to expand the platform to connect more businesses with community projects and charities to support social and environmental causes.

Table 1: Overview of various food sharing enterprises (Alexander and Smaje, 2008; Mazzucchelli et al., 2021).

3. Lowering the Quantity of Food Waste And The Environmental Burdens

Concrete steps to limit the quantity of food waste are required to reduce the environmental effects of food supply networks. The recent policies adopted in Europe to address the issue of food waste are thoroughly examined (Priefer et al., 2016). The introduction of economic measures (e.g., short supply chains for agricultural products), voluntary initiatives (e.g., voluntary commitments by producers and consumers, food donation, communication, and labelling), and regulatory measures (e.g., mandatory targets for reducing food waste, taxation schemes for waste treatment) is covered by the authors. Sustainable production entails controlling food surplus and overproduction at the beginning of the food supply chain, as well as transferring knowledge and advancing technology, particularly in developing nations, to prevent waste. Food availability in distribution and consumption should not exceed what is truly required for food safety, and any surplus should be given to those who have more difficult access to basic nourishment (Papargyropoulou et al., 2014).

In order to encourage improved meal planning in terms of food amount and kind, it is also critical to increase consumer awareness. In this regard, changing to a more fruit- and vegetable-rich diet would not necessarily reduce the amount of food waste because these food categories typically generate a high amount of avoidable waste, but generally speaking, the production of fruit and vegetables has less of an impact on the environment than that of animal products (Nemecek et al., 2016; Poore and Nemecek, 2018; Sinkko et al., 2019). Increasing packaging technology to extend the shelf life of perishable goods is another waste prevention strategy (Heller et al., 2019; Molina-Besch et al., 2019; Nemecek et al., 2016). When avoidance is not an option, converting food waste into compost and animal feed is a good choice in accordance with the waste hierarchy principles. Finally, energy recovery techniques like anaerobic digestion and incineration, as well as landfilling, should only be used as a last resort (Papargyropoulou et al., 2014).

Despite the extensive number of strategies suggested to reduce food waste, the argument about how successful they are is still very much in play. For instance, Mourad (2016) reintroduces the subject to the larger discussion about the strong and weak sustainability of production and consumption systems (O'Rourke and Lollo, 2015), contending that prevention based solely on efficiency optimisation is weak because it frequently depends on voluntary commitments that are, despite being subordinate to economic profit and the preservation of the status quo in the food markets, are subordinate to these goals. Strong waste avoidance strategies would entail streamlining the supply chains for commodities, improving the social and economic ties between producers and consumers, and balancing consumption patterns with the seasons. To significantly reduce environmental impact, alternative food systems must be more efficient than large-scale industrial systems (Nemecek et al., 2016). A fundamental rethinking of production and consumption paradigms is more successful than initiatives that anticipate technological advancements in food conservation through enhanced packaging or an increase in the efficiency of waste energy recovery or treatment (Bernstad Saraiva Schott and Andersson, 2015).

4. Existing Approach

Although there are numerous groups that operate in the subject of distributing extra food, there are also some drawbacks. There are a few frequent drawbacks of using established organisations. Several already operating organisations might only be able to serve a small number of towns or geographical areas. They may find it challenging to reach a larger audience and make a bigger effect as a result. Certain organisations might only have a certain amount of infrastructure, personnel, or resources available. They may find it challenging to expand their activities and assist more individuals in need as a result (Mazzucchelli et al., 2021). Some organisations could lack creativity and neglect to adopt new technologies or investigate novel methods for distributing surplus food. In a market that is undergoing significant change, this may make them less competitive and relevant. It may be difficult for certain groups to continue their operations and increase their effect due to a lack of funds. Certain businesses could use ineffective methods for gathering, handling, and distributing excess food. This may lead to resource wastage, inefficiency, and a diminished impact. These drawbacks demonstrate how innovation, scalability, sustainability, and efficiency are required in the field of excess food redistribution (Harvey et al., 2020).

As a social enterprise, we are working to address the following drawbacks of current organisations through our enterprise for redistributing extra food with the use of a mobile application. By utilising a mobile application that may link donors and non-profit groups across regions and communities, our business hopes to have a wide audience. The effect and reach of initiatives to distribute leftover food can be increased as a result. Our company is a social enterprise, and it makes money in several ways. The activities may be scaled up and more people in need can be served by using this income to increase resource, personnel, or infrastructural capacity. Our company is working to embrace new technologies and investigate fresh strategies for distributing surplus food. The use of the mobile application can improve the effectiveness of surplus food redistribution by streamlining operations. Our company has a variety of income streams, including sponsored content, in-app advertising, and partnerships and collaborations. This can support the enterprise's long-term viability and capacity to grow its influence. Our business attempts to create effective procedures for gathering, managing, and distributing extra food. This can save waste and enhance the overall effectiveness of initiatives to distribute leftover food. These initiatives may contribute to the development of a surplus food redistribution strategy that is more effective, scalable, and sustainable while maximising social benefits (Harvey et al., 2020).

Our business is built on a smartphone application that makes it simpler for non-profit organisations and food donors to connect and set up the redistribution of excess food. The procedure may be made more effective and simplified with the help of the mobile application, which also has a wider audience. It is a social enterprise, which is a company that puts social effect before profit. The business makes money through collaborations and partnerships with businesses, in-app advertising, and sponsored content. The enterprise's mission is supported by the money utilised to maintain and develop it. It has several sources of income, which might increase its sustainability and stability. The company can look at other income streams, such as product sales, subscription-based services, or corporate partnerships, in addition to alliances and collaborations. These adaptations can offer a special and efficient method for distributing extra food and have a hugely beneficial social impact.

5. Flow of Operation

5.1 Data Collection of Both Buyers and Donors

Basically, our application will work on getting information about the hotels and restaurants, and it will be stored in the application and same about the receivers too. Like where people suffer from lack of food and people who can't get food late at night. Using this database, we will get to know where the food is available and quantity too. In this application we will get notification about user's name, a timestamp, type of food, quantity and associated address and contact number of donors when they willing to donate. From the given information, our team moves to that hotel or restaurants and collect it.

5.2 Receiving and Analysing

Once we get notification from the donors, we will move to their place and collect foods. We'll sort it into the categories and use it to structure food distribution and shelve or refrigerate the food for later use. Then we will analyse the food quality and quantity by ensuring that food providing by us will be good. We will also separate out foods that are visibly damaged, rotting, or otherwise believed to be unsafe and foods that came in bulk, since these foods also require "special treatment." Then through database we will approach various people who has food scarcity (fig 3).

Figure 3 – Workflow of the Enterprise

5.3 Storage If Necessary

Since most of the food we expect as donations is already prepared food or deli foods like chicken, roasted or fried, curries, main dishes, meals, cooked vegetables, rice, soups etc., While most of them will last for 2 or 3 days with refrigeration or freezing based on the requirement, we will facilitate the required appliances. We'll try to deliver this kind of food to the clients as safely as possible before it perishes. Other canned foods and shelf-stable foods which will last for a longer period will also be properly stored and checked in timely intervals. Insulated transport containers are among the most often used methods for storing and distributing prepared food. These containers are made to maintain the proper temperature for the food while it is being transported. From little coolers to big catering boxes, they are available in a range of dimensions. The food is kept at the proper temperature for a long time in the containers since they are constructed of insulated materials. Plastic containers are a practical choice for preserving prepared food because they are inexpensive. They are lightweight, available in a range of sizes and forms, and simple to transport. To guarantee that the food stays fresh, look for containers with airtight lids that are made of food-grade materials. Aluminium foil is a versatile material that may be used to package prepared food for delivery. It may be used to wrap several different items and is inexpensive and lightweight. Aluminium foil is not the ideal choice for long-term storage, it should be noted, since it is not airtight. Reusable silicone bags are a more economical and environmentally friendly way to store prepared food. They may be reused again and are strong and simple to clean. Additionally, they are airtight, which preserves the food's freshness. Homemade soups, stews, and other prepared dishes are frequently stored in Mason jars. They are reasonably priced and are available in several sizes. They may be used in the refrigerator or freezer and are also sealed. Cardboard boxes are a convenient and inexpensive way to deliver prepared meals. To help keep the food fresh, they can be coated with plastic bags or aluminium foil. Cardboard boxes are not airtight; thus, they are not the ideal choice for long-term storage, it is crucial to remember. According to recent reports, timely refrigerated truck delivery of fresh produce and perishable commodities is crucial to ensuring their safe arrival at delivery sites(Davis et al., 2014).

5.4 Selling

We plan to charge the lowest price possible for each food product to cover the costs to run this enterprise. Because funds are required for transport, storage, packaging, application services and other costs. This enterprise is primarily created to try and reduce food wastage and provide food to people who need it.

6. Feasibility and Scope

Due to the high rates of food waste and food poverty, there is a great need for excess food redistribution. The smartphone app may establish connections between food givers and charitable institutions, making it simpler to distribute extra food. The mobile application needs technological know-how and resources to develop. To draw and keep users, the mobile application has to be user-friendly, safe, and effective. The business model has potential revenue streams from partnerships and collaborations with organizations, in-app advertising, and sponsored content. Start-up costs are estimated to be covered by investments or grants. Profitability is projected within two years of operation, and significant revenue growth is expected with a growing user base and

partnerships. Legal difficulties might arise from liability concerns and adherence to food safety requirements. The social company must be run in accordance with the appropriate legal frameworks, licences, and permissions. The enterprise's workflow is straightforward and effective. The success of the company depends on developing enduring relationships with food donors, non-profit groups, and governmental bodies. Marketing campaigns must be successful in drawing in users, keeping them engaged, and highlighting the social benefits of the mobile application. The feasibility analysis indicates that the business concept for surplus food redistribution via a mobile application as a social company is practical and has the potential to both generate cash and have a beneficial social impact. To guarantee the enterprise's success, nevertheless, meticulous planning, execution, continuing monitoring, and adaptability are required.

7. Future Prospects

As a social venture, the enterprise for redistributing leftover food with the use of a mobile application has bright future potential. Here are a few prospective future developments.

As our core service, we intend to develop an app that links donors with food producers. Through the application itself, we strive to further develop the bond between the donor and the receiver. Then, this application will result in the provision of work unemployed people for tasks including transportation, running stalls, quality control, etc. There is a global need for extra food to be distributed, not just in one area or nation. To reach a wider audience and have a greater influence, the company can grow into other areas and nations. To boost income and sustainability, the company might look into new revenue opportunities including product sales, subscription-based services, or business alliances. The firm may incorporate new technologies as they emerge, such as virtual reality, blockchain, or artificial intelligence, to improve its offerings and efficiency. To decrease food waste and boost food security, the business can campaign for legislative reforms at the local, state, and federal levels. This advocacy may contribute to the development of more hospitable conditions for social entrepreneurs and the redistribution of surplus food. To increase its effect and sustainability, the company might work with other social companies that share its mission and values. Overall, the company has promising future prospects with tremendous room for expansion and influence. The business may go on innovating, growing, and cooperating to build a more just and sustainable food system while having a positive social effect.

8. Conclusion

A potential way to reduce food waste and address food insecurity at the same time is to use mobile apps to share surplus food. Through the use of technology, surplus food can be distributed to those in need, reducing the amount of food waste that ends up in landfills and giving people who wouldn't otherwise have access to it access to nourishment. While assuring food safety and quality is a challenge when implementing such applications, these obstacles can be overcome with careful planning and execution. Additionally, mobile apps can promote community involvement in addressing these problems and offer a forum for interacting with others who share an interest in food waste and hunger. The support and participation of people and communities around the world are essential for the success of mobile apps for the redistribution of surplus food.

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